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SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY OF BACTERIAL CULTURE USING VITEK-2 FROM SPUTUM FOR DETECTING KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIA AND ACINETOBACTER BAUMANII BACTERIA IN PNEUMONIA PATIENTS AT HAJI ADAM MALIK GENERAL HOSPITAL MEDAN

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Abstract

Introduction: Nosocomial infections are a cause of worldwide morbidity and mortality, a problem is getting worsen when nosocomial pathogens get antibiotic resistance. In Asian countries, antimicrobial resistance to common pathogens of Hospital-Acquired Pneumonia (HAP). Based on Microbiological culture data reports at H. Adam Malik General Hospital in 2017 within 2622 sputum isolates, the most common was Klebsiella pneumonia (16.55%) and Acinetobacter baumannii (17.6%). Detection of bacteria that produce extended-spectrum betalactamase (ESBL) is very important for infection control and epidemiological surveillance. The method used is VITEK-2 and PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction).

Aim: To evaluate the sensitivity and specificity values in the diagnostic test of bacterial sputum culture examination with VITEK-2 and PCR in detecting *K. pneumonia* and *A.baumannii* bacterias.

Methods: The diagnostic test uses primary data based on the results of sputum culture and secondary data based on medical records in pneumonia patients who are hospitalized in H. Adam Malik General Hospital Medan. The sampling technique uses consecutive sampling method on 50 respondents. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.

Result: The diagnostic test results using the VITEK-2 test in detecting both *K. pneumonia* and *A. baumannii* showed sensitivity (93%) and specificity (100%). The evaluation of sensitivity and specificity in detecting *K. pneumonia* was (93.3%) and (100%) higher than in detecting *A.baumannii* was (76.4%) and (100%).

Conclusion: VITEK-2 method can be used in diagnosis and screening in detecting bacteria *K. pneumonia* and *A.baumannii* in pneumonia. The sensitivity value of this method is higher in detection of *K. pneumonia* than *A.baumannii*.

Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a growing public health crisis throughout the world and has been recognized as an important global health problem for the past several decades. Antibiotic resistance occurs when bacteria develop the ability to defeat drugs designed to kill these bacteria. It is estimated that mortality rate in 50,000 lives per year are estimated due to infection problems and antibiotic resistance in the US and Europe.¹ The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention in the United States estimates that every year there are 23,000 deaths caused of AMR.² Based on Microbiological culture data reports obtained from H. Adam Malik General Hospital from January to December in 2017, there were 2622 sputum isolates where the highest prevalence of *K. pneumonia* was 16.55% and *A. baumannii* was 17.6%.

Nowadays in Asian countries, antimicrobial resistance with multidrug resistant (MDR) found most common in hospital-acquired pneumonia (HAP) patients including *Acinetobacter spp.* and *K. pneumoniae species*.³ Data from the United States the percentage of *A. baumannii* isolates that are resistant to imipenem has increased from an average of 10% between 1999 and 2005 to 48% in 2008, and meropenem resistance has increased from 19% to 57.4% over the same time period.⁴ Study in Nepal (2018) of the species *A. baumannii* (41%) was followed by *K. pneumoniae* (28%). In Singapore, ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae, especially *Klebsiella spp.*, has increased

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by 35% - 40%. Study in Brazil in (2019) found isolates of *K. pneumoniae* (n = 21, 84%) classified as MDR. Research in Brazil in 2018 as many as 25 isolates of *K. pneumoniae* produced ESBL, carbapenemase, and carried the 72% blaCTX-M gene.⁵

Another study in Indonesia at Dr Soetomo Hospital in Surabaya, the detection of ESBLs gene, the CTX-M gene, was isolated (55.6%) of *K. pneumoniae*.⁶ Detection of bacteria that produce ESBL is very important for infection control and epidemiological surveillance. PCR is considered the gold standard for evaluation of testing methods. Study with Vitek2 about ESBL identification is based on the inhibitory effect of cefepime, cefotaxime, and ceftazidime and/or with clavulanic acid, the highest sensitivity was (73%-79%).^{7,8} Study in 2008 found the sensitivity and specificity ESBL detection was (78.8% and 80.6%).⁹ Research in France states that the sensitivity and specificity values for the Vitek 2 confirmation test for identification of *K. pneumoniae* are (91.8% /100%) and (91.8% / 100%) ESBL.¹⁰

Method

This study is an observational analytic study with a diagnostic test design. This study was carried out among 50 pneumonia patients that hospitalized in the internal medicine and lung wards of H. Adam Malik General Hospital Medan who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria since August 2019. The inclusion criteria were age ≥ 18 years, diagnosed pneumonia according to clinical, laboratory and radiology based on medical record. Exclusion criteria was inadequate sputum samples.

The data was collected through primary data based on result from determination bacterial gene mutations that cause resistance in pneumonia using the molecular PCR method carried out in the Integrated Laboratory of the Faculty of Medicine, University of North Sumatra and secondary data using medical record data included age, sex and diagnosed pneumonia. Data were analyzed using SPSS 20th in evaluating the sensitivity and specificity of bacterial culture using VITEK-2 in detecting *A. baumannii* and *K. pneumoniae*.

Result

The average age of respondents in this study was 55.50 years, of which were (70%) men and women (30%). All of samples from 50 sputum showed that result based on cultured bacteria with Vitek 2 found a bacterial growth of (90%) samples, consisting of *K. pneumoniae* (33.3%), *A. baumannii* (28.8%), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (20%), *Acinetobacter iwoffii* (4.4%), *E.coli* (2.2%), *Staphylococcus hemolyticus* (2%), *Streptococcus crista* (6.6%) and *Enterobacter cloaca* (2.2%).

The data from PCR found there were *K. pneumoniae* detected (48.4%) and *A. baumannii* 17 (51.5%).

The prevalence of ESBL was found as many (35.5%), where (93.7%) were found in the bacteria *K. pneumoniae*, *A.baumannii* (0.03%), and *E. coli* (6%). The *Klasiella pneumoniae* bacteria had the CTX M gene (93.7%) and the OXA gene (31.2%) and (25%) had the CTXM and OXA genes. Whereas *Acinetobacter baumannii* has the CTX M gene (17.6%), the OXA gene (23.5%) and the CTXM and OXA genes together (5.8%). (Table 4.1)

Based on diagnostic test results using VITEK-2 in detecting *K. pneumoniae* and/or *A.baumannii* found sensitivity (93%) and specificity (100%). This shows that VITEK-2 method is more accurate in terms of diagnostic than *K. pneumoniae* and/or *A.baumannii* bacterial. (Table 2)

The result of VITEK-2 for diagnostic test in detecting *K. pneumoniae* found sensitivity (93.3%) and specificity (100%). This shows that the VITEK-2 method is more accurate in diagnostic terms than screening for *K. pneumoniae* bacterial. (Table 3)

The result of VITEK-2 diagnostic test results in detecting *A. baumannii* found sensitivity (76.4%) and specificity (100%). This shows that the VITEK-2 method is more accurate in terms of diagnostics than screening for *A.baumannii* bacterial. (Table 4)

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Table 1. Distribution characteristics subject.

Variable	n (%)
Age (Years)	55,5 (25-86)
Sex	
Man	35 (70%)
Women	15 (30%)
Bacterial Identification using Vitek2	
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	15 (33,3%)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	13 (28,8%)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	9 (20%)
<i>Acinetobacter iwoffii</i>	2 (4,4%)
<i>E. coli</i>	1 (2,2%)
<i>Staphylococcus hemolyticus</i>	1 (2,2%)
<i>Streptococcus crista</i>	3 (6,6%)
<i>Enterococcus cloaca</i>	1 (2,2%)
Identification ESBL using Vitek2	16 (35,5%)
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	15 (93,7%)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	0
<i>E. coli</i>	1 (6,2%)
Bacterial identification using PCR	
<i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>	16 (48,4%)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	17(51,5%)
Genotype ESBL <i>K.pneumonia</i>	
CTX-M	15 (93,7%)
OXA	5 (31,2%)
CTX-M + OXA	4 (25%)
Genotype ESBL <i>A. baumannii</i>	
CTX-M	3(17,6%)
OXA	4(23,5%)
CTX-M + OXA	1(5,8%)

Table 2. The sensitivity and specificity test of bacterial culture in detecting *K. pneumonia* and/or *A. baumannii*

		Positive	Negative	Total
Bacteria Cultured	Positive	28	0	28
	Negative	2	20	22
	Total	30	20	50

Table 3. The sensitivity and specificity test of bacterial culture in detecting *K. pneumonia*

		Positive	Negative	Total
Bacteria Cultured	Positive	15	0	15
	Negative	1	34	35
	Total	16	34	50

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Table 4. The sensitivity and specificity test of bacterial culture in detecting *A. baumannii*

		Positive	Negative	Total
Bacteria Cultured	Positive	13	0	13
	Negative	4	33	37
	Total	17	33	50

Discussion

In this study, VITEK-2 method in detecting the bacteria *K. pneumonia* and/or *A. baumannii* was found sensitivity (93%) and specificity (100%) in patients with pneumonia, which specifically showed that ability of VITEK-2 in detecting *A. baumannii* had sensitivity (76.4%) and specificity (100%) and *K. pneumonia* had sensitivity (93.3%) and specificity (100%). This study is in line with the study of Joyanes et al., was using 198 clinical isolates in which it identified *A. baumannii* with sensitivity (76%).¹¹ The same result is also found in Bobenchik study (2015) at Los Angeles where a value of sensitivity (92.7%) was obtained in detecting *A. baumannii*.¹² Other studies on the VITEK-2 method show satisfactory results in detecting gram-negative bacteria such as *A. baumannii* and *K. pneumonia*. Ling et al, of 281 isolates found sensitivity (95%). Nakasone et al. and Gherardi et al. analyzed 181 and 95 gram-negatives and obtained sensitivity (96.7%) and (100%) with the VITEK-2 system.^{13,14} Study in Switzerland showed a high specificity value (90.4%) in detecting *K. pneumonia*.¹⁵

Extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) are a large groups bacterial, rapidly growing group of enzymes that provide resistance to oxymino cephalosporins and monobactams and are inhibited by clavulanates. Early detection that show accurate and reliable result test is needed of management infection. In this study found a lower prevalence of ESBL (35.5%), even though study Horie et al. showed higher prevalence of ESBL (41.9%) in Europe and the Mediterranean, (52.9%) in Latin America and (47.2%) in the Asia Pacific region.¹⁶ Other researchers in Ethiopia from 426 samples identified as much ESBL (57.7%) also survey conducted at a hospital in East Africa reported the overall proportion of ESBL was collected (42%).^{17,18}

Klebsiella pneumoniae is one of the pathogens that cause pneumonia and results in a wide range of infections causing major morbidity and mortality. Novel study found that the potential of many antimicrobial agents has been resistant to this bacterium. ESBL is known to be an enzyme produced by bacteria to fight betalactam antibiotics.¹⁹ In the last decade, ESBL type CTX-M has replaced the TEM and SHV types and has become the dominant isolate in Enterobacteriaceae clinically. We found a high prevalence of CTXM in *K. pneumonia* (100%) bacterial. Alongside with study in Lebanon (2014) confirmed that 68 ESBL isolates *K.pneumonia* (86.7%) containing CTX-M.²⁰ Research in the United States in 1990 showed that the prevalence of blaCTX-M was still rare (25%) in 2000 but increased rapidly in 2005 (90%).²¹ Research in New York also shows the alignment of the increase in the prevalence of blaCTX-M *K. pneumonia* showed significant increased in 2005 to 2009 (1.7%) and in 2010 to 2012 (26.4%) ($p < 0.0001$).²²

Carbapenem has been the drug of choice for the treatment of serious infections caused by strains of Enterobacteriaceae that produce β -lactamase (ESBL). The emergence of carbapenem resistance has been increasingly reported among Enterobacteriaceae and is a major clinical problem. The most common mechanism for carbapenem resistance in *K. pneumoniae* is the production of carbapenemases.²³ Previous study have been reported Class D carbapenemases obtained mainly in *Acinetobacter* spp. Oxacillinase was first identified from isolates of *K. pneumonia* in Istanbul, Turkey.²⁴ *Acinetobacter baumannii* is an opportunistic pathogen that is often involved in outbreaks of infection. Isolates resistant to several *A. baumannii* drugs have been reported to increase over the past decade, possibly as a consequence of extensive use of antimicrobial agents.²⁵ Several studies focusing on carbapenem resistance in *A. baumannii* have been reported, mostly related to β -lactamase production. *A. baumannii* also produces intrinsic β -lactamase which is an oxasilinase represented by the OXA variant.^{26,27}

However, in our study, the prevalence of the OXA gene in *A. baumannii* was still low (23.5%) but contained CTXM gene expression (17.6%) that in line with study in Iran that found CTXM gene expression also appeared (20%) in 100 *A. baumannii* isolates.²⁸ Studies in Haiti and India also showed the low prevalence of CTXM gene expression. Despite the high prevalence of blaCTX-M-15 in Enterobacteriaceae, the gene is still rarely identified in *A. baumannii*. This may be due to the fact that plasmids carrying blaCTX-M-15 have a narrow host range and

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cannot replicate within *A. baumannii*, it is possible that the integration of the ISEcp1-blaCTX-M-15 element into the chromosome *A. baumannii* may have occurred.²⁹

Conclusion

This study concluded that VITEK-2 is a diagnostic support tool with good sensitivity and specificity, so it can use to identify the *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* bacteria that cause pneumonia. It is known about the spread of ESBL genotypes that are still low, especially CTX-M and OXA which are found in the bacteria *K. pneumonia* and *A. Baumannii*, so should be concern in the management of infectious patients where the high prevalence of ESBL genotypes will affect the morbidity, mortality, period care, and high maintenance costs in inpatients pneumonia

References

- [1] Ali et al. 2017 "Antimicrobial Resistance Mechanisms and Potential Synthetic Treatments." www.future-science.com.
- [2] Miller et al. 2016. "Antibiotic Resistance and Regulation of the Gram-Negative Bacterial Outer Membrane Barrier by Host Innate Immune Molecules." *mBio* 7(5).
- [3] Lagamayo et al. 2008. "Antimicrobial Resistance in Major Pathogens of Hospital-Acquired Pneumonia in Asian Countries." *American Journal of Infection Control* 36(4 SUPPL.).
- [4] Evans et al. 2014. "OXA β -Lactamases." *Clinical Microbiology Reviews* 27(2): 241–63.
- [5] Ferreira et al. 2019. "High Prevalence of Multidrug-Resistant *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* Harboring Several Virulence and β -Lactamase Encoding Genes in a Brazilian Intensive Care Unit." *Frontiers in Microbiology* 10(JAN).
- [6] Severin et al. 2010. "Molecular Characterization of Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamases in Clinical *Escherichia Coli* and *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* Isolates from Surabaya, Indonesia." *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy* 65(3): 465–69.
- [7] Ne Garrec et al. 2011. "Comparison of Nine Phenotypic Methods for Detection of Extended-Spectrum-Lactamase Production by Enterobacteriaceae." *Journal Of Clinical Microbiology* 49(3): 1048–57.
- [8] Spanu et al. 2006. "Evaluation of the New VITEK 2 Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) Test for Rapid Detection of ESBL Production in Enterobacteriaceae Isolates." *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 44(9): 3257–62.
- [9] Färber, J. et al. 2008. "Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase Detection with Different Panels for Automated Susceptibility Testing and with a Chromogenic Medium." *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 46(11): 3721–27.
- [10] Robin et al. 2008. "Evaluation of the Vitek-2 Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase Test against Non-Duplicate Strains of Enterobacteriaceae Producing a Broad Diversity of Well-Characterised β -Lactamases." *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 14(2): 148–54.
- [11] Joyanes, P., M. D.C. Conejo, L. Martínez-Martínez, and E. J. Perea. 2001. "Evaluation of the VITEK 2 System for the Identification and Susceptibility Testing of Three Species of Nonfermenting Gram-Negative Rods Frequently Isolated from Clinical Samples." *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 39(9): 3247–53.
- [12] Bobenchik et al. 2017. "Performance of Vitek 2 for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing of *Acinetobacter Baumannii*, *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*, and *Stenotrophomonas Maltophilia* with Vitek 2 (2009 FDA) and CLSI M100S
- [13] Gherardi et al. 2012. "Comparative Evaluation of the Vitek-2 Compact and Phoenix Systems for Rapid Identification and Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing Directly from Blood Cultures of Gram-Negative and Gram-Positive Isolates." *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease* 72(1): 20–31.
- [14] Nakasone et al. 2007. "Laboratory-Based Evaluation of the Colorimetric VITEK-2 Compact System for Species Identification and of the Advanced Expert System for Detection of Antimicrobial Resistances: VITEK-2 Compact System Identification and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing." *Diagnostic Microbiology and Infectious Disease* 58(2): 191–98.
- [15] Funke et al. 1998. "Evaluation of the VITEK 2 System for Rapid Identification of Medically Relevant Gram-Negative Rods." *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 36(7): 1948–52.

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- [16] Horie et al. 2018. "Isolation of ESBL-Producing Bacteria from Sputum in Community-Acquired Pneumonia or Healthcare-Associated Pneumonia Does Not Indicate the Need for Antibiotics with Activity against This Class." *Internal Medicine* 57(4): 487–95.
- [17] Teklu et al. 2019. "Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase Production and Multi-Drug Resistance among Enterobacteriaceae Isolated in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia." *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control* 8(1): 39.
- [18] Abrar et al. 2018. "Prevalence of Extended-Spectrum- β -Lactamase-Producing Enterobacteriaceae: First Systematic Meta-Analysis Report from Pakistan." *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control* 7(1).
- [19] Maleki, Nafiseh et al. 2018. "Prevalence of CTX-M and TEM β -Lactamases in Klebsiella Pneumoniae Isolates from Patients with Urinary Tract Infection, Al-Zahra Hospital, Isfahan, Iran." *Advanced Biomedical Research* 7(1): 10.
- [20] Obeid Charrouf, F. et al. 2014. "Characterization of Resistance Genes in 68ESBL-Producing Klebsiella Pneumonia in Lebanon." *Medecine et Maladies Infectieuses* 44(11–12): 535–38.
- [21] Lewis et al. 2007. "First Report of the Emergence of CTX-M-Type Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamases (ESBLs) as the Predominant ESBL Isolated in a U.S. Health Care System." *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy* 51(11): 4015–21.
- [22] Zhao et al. 2013. "Epidemiology and Genetics of CTX-M Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamases in Gram-Negative Bacteria." *Critical Reviews in Microbiology* 39(1): 79–101.
- [23] Miriagou, V. et al. 2010. "Acquired Carbapenemases in Gram-Negative Bacterial Pathogens: Detection and Surveillance Issues." *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 16(2): 112–22.
- [24] Poirel et al. 2004. "Emergence of Oxacillinase-Mediated Resistance to Imipenem in Klebsiella Pneumoniae." *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 48(1): 15–22.
- [25] Coelho et al. 2004. "Multiresistant Acinetobacter in the UK: How Big a Threat?" *Journal of Hospital Infection* 58(3): 167–69.
- [26] Brown et al. 2005. "Characterisation of OXA-51, a Novel Class D Carbapenemase Found in Genetically Unrelated Clinical Strains of Acinetobacter Baumannii from Argentina." *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 11(1): 15–23.
- [27] Héritier et al. 2005. "Characterization of the Naturally Occurring Oxacillinase of Acinetobacter Baumannii." *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 49(10): 4174–79.
- [28] Safari et al. 2015. "Prevalence of ESBL and MBL Encoding Genes in Acinetobacter Baumannii Strains Isolated from Patients of Intensive Care Units (ICU)." *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* 22(4): 424–29.
- [29] Potron et al. 2011. "Genetic Features of CTX-M-15-Producing Acinetobacter Baumannii from Haiti." *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 55(12): 5946–48.